

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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ABOUT THE OAEBU DATA TRUST EFFORT

Originating in 2015, the OAeBU Data Trust effort has brought over 100 individuals across five continents together to surface and address the issues that complicate the analysis and use of book usage metrics for decision-making and open-access advocacy. To date, the project has documented the complex OAeBU data supply chain,² launched pilots of open-source infrastructure for a usage data trust, and facilitated workshops to understand the ways in which scholars and specific staff roles at libraries, publishers, and publishing platforms and services rely on OAeBU data. While these use cases were documented to inform data trust service development, the project team recognizes that they provide broader insights into the evolving analytics and linked-data demands across the scholarly communications ecosystem.

METHODOLOGY

This document evolved from the outputs of multiple virtual ideation sessions and workshops among peer stakeholder groups. These community-oriented feedback mechanisms were advertised via the OAeBU Data Trust effort's communities of practice. Co-Editors Drummond and Hawkins translated meeting and asynchronous ideation outputs into a preliminary use case document, which was shared back for public comment via the project's communities of practice and social media.³ Public comment was incorporated into this document, with notes offered by community members included at the end of each section. Within this document, the staff roles within commercial publishers that work with usage data are identified as personas. Then, use cases are listed with descriptions of why usage data is important or how it is applied for a given use case. Specific questions or queries of usage data that surfaced in discussion are noted.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Book publishers, publishing platforms and services, and libraries all rely on book usage data to inform their operations. Across these industries, staff must address the burden of managing and curating usage data provisioned in COUNTER-compliant and non-compliant reports,

1 https://educopia.org/data_trust/ and <https://zenodo.org/communities/oaebu>

2 Clarke, Michael, & Ricci, Laura. (2021, April 9). OA Books Supply Chain Mapping Report. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4681725>

3 The OAeBU project's processes for communities of practice development and use case development are published in Drummond, Christina (2020). "Engaging Stakeholder Networks to Support Global OA Monograph Usage Analytics," Collaborative Librarianship: Vol. 12 : Iss. 2 , Article 9. <https://digitalcommons.du.edu/collaborativelibrarianship/vol12/iss2/9>

APIs, dashboards, and spreadsheets. These institutions individually manage, compile, and link usage data metrics, some of which are provisioned via dashboard services for users ranging from scholars, research offices and funding agencies, to editors, collections and acquisitions managers, and administrative decision makers.

While the term “usage data” is often used today to refer to web analytics reports that tally page visits and file downloads, the use cases herein document a near future where linked usage data analytics regularly inform book publishing and scholarly communications operations. Publishers and libraries expressed interest in using OAeBU data analytics to inform overall investment, strategy and fundraising in OA programs. They noted how data on the location and context of access to OA eBooks can inform book marketing and dissemination strategy, acquisitions and collections development, and scholars’ promotion and tenure. OAeBU data also surfaced as vital to supporting the promotion of OA publication among scholars and to illustrating institutional impact on the local and global stage. Linked contextual usage data can illustrate how OA books reach targeted audiences in classrooms, among scholars, within industry, and among policy-makers.

OAeBU data is poised to inform customer service relationships as publishers and libraries seek to appreciate service provider niches, evaluate book hosting and dissemination arrangements, and understand what is returned from their OA investments. Simultaneously, publishing platforms and services leverage usage data to inform the research, development, sales, and marketing of their own infrastructure.

Diverse models for OA book publishers, from university or library-based publishers to commercial publisher OA teams, surfaced many common functional needs of OAeBU data for publishers as shown in the graphic below. However, their structures resulted in unique needs tied to administrative and sales reporting, as is reflected in their individual use cases.

COMMERCIAL PUBLISHER OA EBOOK USAGE (OAEBU) DATA USE CASES

OA-focused commercial publishing teams apply OAeBU data to support marketing, sales, and OA program strategy. They also provide OAeBU data to support editorial processes and authors. OAeBU data may surface access trends and discovery-platform audience niches while also allowing editors and authors to benchmark OA eBooks against comparable books by leveraging usage data as a digital counterpart to traditional sales data. Staff roles that may interact with OAeBU data span OA management, strategy, market intelligence, marketing, sales, editorial and acquisitions, and IT.

Multiple issues make it difficult to realize the benefits of working with OAeBU data. Practices for analyzing OA usage data alongside non-OA and print sales data are developing. Situating internal OAeBU data alongside aggregator reports is a manual, time-intensive process riddled with technical challenges stemming from evolving standards and varying levels of data compatibility and existing standards adoption. Notably, there is also no existing mechanism to contextualize OAeBU data against competitor benchmarks or across the OAeBU data landscape.

OA Program

Marketing

Sales

Editorial

Use Case 1.

Inform internal OA program strategy

Personas

"Which books in which editorial departments could benefit the most from efforts to diversity and increase readership?"

"Did the OA version help those who'd benefit from using the book access it?"

a. Provide usage reports

Why | How

- i. to demonstrate OA strategy, importance, and impact to internal audiences
- ii. to show eBook usage by audience and discipline over book lifespan
- iii. to show how operational changes shift engagement patterns
 1. involving usage by platform, country, discipline
 2. across known existing and anonymous customers
- iv. to track and demonstrate Open Access impact on expanding readership
 1. by illustrating whether an OA version increases book readership and access over time
 2. by illustrating if a book about a region was used within that region
 3. by adding context for books in smaller topic areas based on comparable usage activity in relevant topic areas
 4. by surfacing potential disciplinary crossover based on usage of comparable titles
 - a. across disciplines
 - b. within target audience communities

"Show what someone can expect from working with us."

"The ability to drill down into the data is important!"

"Each author and book has its own niche audience."

"I'd like to be able to say here's how we expect the OA content to be accessed..."

Note: Book usage data stakeholders include authors, OA funders such as national funding bodies, library consortia, community-sourced funding schemes, learned societies, etc.

b. Understand eBook audiences

- i. to establish OA program profile or niche
- ii. to understand how OA readership patterns differ from non-OA
 1. for public access to publicly funded research outputs
 2. for specific geographic regions
- iii. to support regional-office strategy development
 1. with internal-facing usage reports for subjects by region and platform
 2. by surfacing areas that merit attention
- iv. to identify matches between funder priorities for specific audience usage and the OA program's strengths and historical usage patterns
e.g. "What is the historical usage of chemistry titles like this in this specific geographic region?"

c. Compare OA program activity against other OA publishing programs via industry benchmarks

- i. for peer publishing programs, i.e. publishers of roughly the same size and type
- ii. for different types of publishers

d. Compare OA book performance against comparable usage benchmarks for a given audience and discipline

- i. to show authors what OA book "success" looks like when working with our OA program
 1. for an individual title based on similar titles
 2. in a discipline for target audiences
e.g. "For books on topic X with a target audience in region Y, this is what OA usage looked like?"
- ii. to project usage based on past trends for similar books
 1. by responding to authors asking, "When can we expect peak engagement based on usage trends?"
- iii. to understand duration of book lifespan
 1. by illustrating when peak usage is expected for a given discipline and audience
e.g. "The trend for books like yours is to see a bump in activity after x years and y years."
- iv. to inform book stakeholders of expected engagement patterns and book impacts

Use Case 2.

Generate external funding impact reports

Personas

"Move the dialogue from 'we published it' to 'here's how the OA version affected the impact.'"

"Support reporting requirements that require universities to show how they achieve impact."

Note: Frequency and granularity of data are important.

Work is needed to define terms and metrics for lifespan, measures, and peak activity.

a. Communicate impacts to stakeholders

- i. by reporting usage by
 1. author institutional affiliation
 2. title
 3. source of download (platform)
 4. geographic region of access
 5. a publisher's core or traditional audiences
 6. author or funder targeted audiences
 7. Note: Each book may have its own success metrics in terms of what its author wants to achieve by going OA.
- ii. by generating reports for
 1. research funders
 - a. usage and engagement tied to
 - i. research area or field
 - ii. mission impact
 1. public policy references
 2. other "broader impacts"
 - iii. geographic / regional usage
 2. groups that fund OA books or whole book series to establish ROI
 - a. learned societies
 - b. research institutes
 - c. charities/NGOs
 - d. corporations
 - e. libraries and library consortia
 3. authors and their research offices
 - a. to establish compliance with funding mandates, e.g. "Support reporting requirement for UK Research Excellence Framework"
 - b. to show 'real world' or broader impacts

Use Case 3.

Support marketing campaigns and strategy

Personas

"The goal is to connect usage activity to promotional campaigns."

Note: campaign may refer to email and/or social media campaigns.

a. Support marketing of OA program

- i. to encourage OA adoption by showing advantages to publishing OA compared to non-OA
 1. compare OA vs. non-OA usage, e.g. *"How do OA books perform compared to non-OA counterparts in this subject area?"*
 2. compare OA vs. non-OA discoverability
 3. illustrate what happens when a book is "flipped to OA"
- ii. to illustrate the global profile, reach, niche of an OA program
 1. show "what one can expect from working with us"
 2. by institution type, region, usage activity
- iii. to develop white papers for stakeholders
 1. industry
 2. higher education
 3. book-series partners and/or funders
 4. authors
 5. funders

b. Support promotions for OA book content and OA authors

- i. to show how promotions affect targeted audience usage by examining activity by date or date range by institution type (e.g. libraries, schools) and regional split by subject
- ii. by understanding content usage and engagement over time, e.g. *"Is usage ongoing? Is something "adopted" or "continuously read?"*
- iii. by providing authors with usage reporting
 1. generating custom, personalized book performance reports showing specific usage on platforms
 - a. following promotion campaigns or launch events
 - b. related to social media activity
 2. providing self-service reporting access so authors can check their own usage directly via
 - a. author-facing dashboards
 - b. automated "personalized book performance" emails

c. Support author recognition

- i. to trigger *"Congratulations - your book is one of the most downloaded"* notifications
- ii. to suggest marketing campaigns based on
 1. top downloaded books
 2. most cited books

Use Case 4.

Inform sales strategy

Personas

"Is there a trend of print sales going up or down after becoming OA?"

Does the trend vary by discipline ?

a. Provide data on what to expect when flipping a title OA

- i. to understand changes in usage after making content OA on a limited basis, e.g. *"What was the impact of making books OA in response to COVID-19 from date X to date Y?"*

b. Illuminate OA impact (+/-) on sales revenue over time

- i. by viewing OA-related sales trends for the time spanning before and after going OA to answer questions
- ii. to understand follow-on print sales related to OA access
- iii. to understand follow-on eBook sales related to OA access

c. Inform pricing strategy

- i. by understanding interactions between OA usage, book margins, and pricing
- ii. by analyzing traditional sales revenue alongside OA revenue streams
- iii. by understanding usage trends for OA content bundles and eBook packages to support sales team offering bundled OA access e.g. *"If there is an eBook package, librarians want to know if they can include access for a discovery POV."*

d. Inform print-edition compensation strategy based on OA usage

- i. to understand if OA access drives print purchases, e.g. at libraries

e. Inform sales strategy for target audiences

- i. to determine discovery platform fit, e.g. *"For a Latin American studies monograph, how did comparable OA titles best reach their intended audience?"*

Use Case 5.

Support editors

Personas

a. Provide usage data for editorial decision-making

- i. to understand average usage for comparable titles within a discipline or subject area
- ii. to inform expansion strategy by identifying disciplines where interest or readership is increasing

b. Inform book commissioning

- i. by providing benchmarked usage data for a book's audience and topic to understand and gauge usage, e.g. *"Is it 'going well' or is it higher or lower than expected?"*

c. Support acquisitions by providing authors with usage reports

- i. to establish the reach of a publisher's OA book dissemination
- ii. to complement print edition sales data
- iii. to support author requests for data demonstrating OA benefits

Use Case 6.

Track OA discovery platform usage activity

Personas

"It is important to show that the target audience successfully accessed the eBook, not just that content was available OA."

a. Ensure OA versions are being discovered

- i. to understand whether OA version is being accessed
- ii. to understand how OA version is being accessed by target audiences

b. Assess ROI for discovery and hosting platforms and services

- i. by comparing usage, impact, and citations across platforms "in the wild"
- ii. to illuminate platform-related usage by target audiences segmented by region, usage "size", discipline
- iii. by surfacing benefits of working with specific dissemination platforms
 1. e.g. "How well does platform X reach our target audience?"
 2. e.g. "Which platform could do the best job if we have to prioritize?"

Use Case 7.

Work towards usage data standards compliance

Personas

a. Ensure reporting meets applicable standards for usage data (e.g. COUNTER)

b. Navigate unclear standards

c. Compile and aggregate platform-provided usage data that is non-COUNTER compliant, legacy (e.g. COUNTER 4), and COUNTER 5

Notes regarding COUNTER usage data

- Not all 'platforms' as defined by COUNTER provide COUNTER-compliant usage reports.
- Non-COUNTER reporting makes usage data aggregation labor-intensive, open to institutional interpretation as to what should be measured, with greater risk of data handling error.